

BOOK REVIEW

Teacher: Seeking the Vocational Archetype by Robert Mitchell
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Central to Robert Mitchell's book *Teacher* is the idea that the true teacher follows a vocation that transcends dispensation of knowledge or advancement up a bureaucratic scale. The true teacher possesses or cultivates a sense of connection, a capacity to stimulate an interplay of conscious and unconscious energies between student and teacher. This stimulation leads toward spiritual bonding and individuation. The student, feeding on a constellation of energies aroused through exposure to the teacher, undergoes psychic maturing, developing fuller healthy individual self-identity by interacting with the teacher (archetypally identified as Mentor, the mythic teacher of Odysseus's son Telemachus in *The Odyssey*). This results in the stimulating of the hero archetype within the pupil, encouraging transformation, while the teacher grows in capacity for mentoring.

The model of psychic development is perhaps best represented via its symbolic manifestation in various renderings of the hero archetype. These manifestations have been analyzed by V. Propp and Joseph Campbell, among others. They involve a youth who goes on a quest that leads through a moment of crisis to achievement of a goal, often facilitated by a powerful gift received from a donor. In simplified form, the hero is the child, the donor a teacher or mentor, the gift an aide to gaining insight, awareness, self-possession, etc. This accomplishment allows the hero to complete the quest and come back to the world a transformed person, ready for greatness. Renderings of this archetypal 'monomyth' occur world-wide in fairy tales and myths as well as in more modern forms such as comic books, superhero movies, and computer games. Many present in symbolic form absorption into a moment of *participation mystique*, a "particular kind of psychological connection" where "the subject cannot clearly distinguish himself from the object but is bound to it by a direct relationship."¹ This melding aids transformation and may rely on the gift of the older guide, the mentor or teacher. We see such patterns in the Han Solo/Obi Wan Kenobi relation in *Star Wars* as well as in the *Rapunzel* or *Sleeping Beauty* figure who achieves awakening through a prince, be he Frog, beast, or eponymous Prince Charming.

Such highfalutin talk about Mitchell's work does it a disservice, as the book is written for the average reader and geared toward students preparing for careers as teachers at the junior- or senior-high school level. Each chapter ends with a question or questions for the would-be teacher to consider, often in light of Jungian psychology, the psycho-philosophical foundation on which Mitchell builds. Part memoir, part case study, part critique, part philosophical and psychological

¹ C.G. Jung, *Psychological Types, The Collected Works*, Vol. 6 (Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 1971), p. 781. Quoted in Mark Winborn, "Participation Mystique: An Overview," International Association for Analytical Psychology, <https://iaap.org/jung-analytical-psychology/short-articles-on-analytical-psychology/participation-mystique-an-overview/>. Accessed 12 October 2024.

exploration, *Teacher* portrays Mitchell's understanding of the role of the teacher and the teacher's importance in what we might call the spiritual development of the child, the movement toward adulthood and psychological health that is so important and, in many ways (Mitchell hints), so at risk in our society. Aware of the belief that American schools are failing youth despite "No Child Left Behind" and other doctrines, Mitchell offers insight from a Depth Psychology perspective into the forces at work in the maturing child and how they can be shaped with the aid of the right helper.

Mitchell describes teaching adolescents at a private American school in Cuernavaca, Mexico, and at a predominately Black girl's Catholic school in Chicago, and also his teacher trainee experiences around Chicago and his experiences as a teacher in or near Santa Cruz, California. He also alludes to earlier non-teaching experiences in France and among peasants in Crete, Italy, and elsewhere, where he interacted with societies that lack the foci on rationality and ideological hegemony that he sees dominating education in the United States. Details on these earlier experiences are missing, but might have helped illustrate some of the experiences described in the book, especially the extra-curricular (to say the least) episode in the cave depicted in the section set in Santa Cruz. Here the rite of maturation seems literally symbolically experienced in the emergence from the cave/womb, providing a bonding experience between students and teacher that is suggestive of initiation rituals among primary cultures. This link perhaps could be illustrated more, though maybe doing so would mitigate the initiatory experience that is directly felt and perhaps subliminally assimilated. The experience would be rationalized in a way that would force it to lose its disturbing qualities, which may be an essential component of the psychic significance of the moment.

The first chapter suggests that the book will offer a memoir of teaching experiences, as Mitchell describes his first teaching job in a private school for American expatriates in Mexico, teaching courses in literature, history, and geometry. This initial experience seems fortunate considering Mitchell's description of his interactions with the American public school system later in the book. The autonomy he enjoyed in Mexico helped him establish a central perspective on teaching, since he "could rely on [his] own passions, intellect, and experience to experiment with approaches to [his] courses" (p. 1). Mitchell hints that his earlier life in France and among peasants in Crete and Italy gave him the important insight that thinking is "as prerational and prehistoric as rational and historical" (p. 11). Insights into prerational processes helped Mitchell understand the development of the child's mind in that, he maintains, ontogeny recapitulates phylogeny—the development of the child's psyche reconfigures the growth of humanity toward modern rationality. This insight helped him develop pedagogical approaches that incorporate the arts, even with topics such as history and geometry. But significantly, learning goes both ways. When challenged by a student who claims that history is irrelevant, Mitchell confronts his own doubts about the value of teaching history as names and events presented as a chronology. He finds himself "trapped in a historical-rational perceptive" that belies "the evolution of consciousness" and the "a-rational component [of consciousness] that dominated human existence far longer than rationality has" (p. 15). He ended up trying to expose students to this deeper perspective, delving beyond rationality.

Mitchell also came to think of the teacher as an integral part of the community, and that "being included in a community [is] different from our usual perception of the goal of the teacher" (p. 21). This recognition, tied to his realization that "the objective of education was to develop

consciousness in the child” (p. 22), was challenged when he moved back to the United States to pursue a higher degree in Education and get certified to teach in American public schools. Chapter 2 relates his search for a degree program, his experiences as a student teacher, and his efforts to secure a full-time teaching position. Even before he starts his degree program, he gets a position at a private, all-girls, largely Black Catholic school on the south side of Chicago. His experience there convinces him even more that teaching involves “commitment.” Pursuing a master’s degree in teaching, he undergoes training that exposes him to various aspects of teaching—including the recommendation that he should not be too “objective and impersonal” (p. 28). The teacher’s goal, he learns, is to “[bridge] the gap between the generations” (p. 30). Mitchell discusses the role of the teaching mentor for the new teacher, and concludes that good teachers utilize skills as storytellers, artists, dramatists, philosophers, and psychologists to achieve their goal of opening the child.

In Chapter 3 the direction of the book shifts, moving from Mitchell’s personal experiences to analyses of vocational objectives. Mitchell claims that good teaching involves “a vocational calling ... from the spirit-voice of the vocational archetype” (p. 44). Some goals he sets involve seeking to live and work in the same community, so the teacher can become an integral component of the social setting; using innovative teaching methodologies; and finding an educational philosophy that incorporates the study of child development. The first of these goals is important because the teacher, as part of the community, engages in a “sacred trust” that helps bond the community, sharing responsibility in the raising, nurturing, and education of the young. This community involvement is enhanced by use of innovative strategies that incorporate storytelling, art, and drama into his teaching. Inspired by courses and lectures offered at the C. G. Jung Center and elsewhere, he finds mentorship for his teaching style in presentations given by Robert Bly, Diane Wolkstein, James Hillman, and others. This mentorship helps him introduce approaches to teaching that facilitate pre-rational and imaginative aspects of psychic development that he feels are more prominent in cultures that are less driven by rationalism than is the US—aspects of life that are important in forming the full human. His education philosophy, he then claims, runs on a different track than that encouraged by dominant forces in US education. Increasingly, Mitchell argues, the government has moved ideological control away from the individual school to the Department of Education. Movements such as No Child Left Behind attempt to “ensure ideological compliance” (p. 53) by regulating funding and testing. These centralized ideologies focus on utilitarianism, using the rhetoric of risk to call for the “evaluation of teachers” whose quality gets “defined in terms of accountability to the goals of the educational bureaucracy” (p. 56). Increased centralization leads to a focus on the development of skills rather than on the development of the person. As Mitchell puts it, “The philosophical governing principle of national educational policy has a direct impact on every classroom teacher” (p. 58). Because of this emphasis, Mitchell feels obliged to examine the utilitarian philosophy and to oppose its effect of prioritizing standardization as against individual development.

Mitchell defines his educational goal in chapter 4 as achieving a “balance between mind and soul, between ... good citizenship and ... individual character” (p. 62). Working toward this goal involves encouraging “the process of mental consciousness” to awaken “the soul” or “natural sentient and imaginative consciousness” and the ability “to examine ... the concept of democracy in cultural, rather than secular, sociopolitical terms” (p. 63). These aims, Mitchell finds, contrast with the overall bureaucratic focus of public schools. This realization leads Mitchell to ask who

he works for: Parents? Children? The institution? This questioning leads to questioning the purpose of education: is the teacher there to provide professional training? Social preparation of functioning citizens? Development of individuality? He concludes that socialization and the cultural formation of identity help unite the citizens of a nation, but also require focus on more than the mind. In helping develop social identification, the teacher becomes a public servant.

But the profession involves an inevitable dichotomy: the teacher serves society (the public trust) but must also serve the child (the sacred trust). Secular utilitarianism as a driving force in the American public school system has put these goals out of balance. Fulfilling the sacred trust requires “autonomy in applying educational theory to classroom practice” (p. 68). But the utilitarian goals of creating a workforce have become dominant, and “the individual is socialized with moral and ethical values and behaviors that are secular, though they purport to be humanistic” (p. 71). As a result, “Achieving one’s highest potential is compromised by secular-utilitarianism that emphasizes the development of the intellect over the nurture of the soul” (p. 72)—i.e., over focus on the sacred trust. The effort to enhance both “the child’s natural sentient and imaginative ways of knowing” and “the development of the intellect” (p. 76) encourages “awakening self-awareness of the sanctity of the individual” (p. 77). This means that the teacher must recognize that “secular humanism is an irresolvable contradiction” since “secular means nonspiritual, but humanism had an inherent spirituality that transcends all religions” (p. 79). This leads Mitchell to consider three objectives behind cultural identify formation: 1. giving the child a sense of belonging to a common cultural continuum that stretches back in time to the origins of the culture; 2. teaching the mythic or cosmological origins of each culture studied in the survey of the human cultural continuum; and 3. developing an adult personality with character that is grounded in a humanistic spirituality. Mitchell connects these goals to the insights of several well-known philosophers and thinkers, including Aristotle and Jean-Jacques Rousseau, as well as more contemporary thinkers such as Allan Bloom, Howard Gardner, Ron Miller, and E. D. Hirsch. These connections lead Mitchell to emphasize teaching skills, cultural identity, and the human potential to acquire self-knowledge, to give students “the courage to seek a more integrated personality” (p. 92).

Intuition, instinct, insight, sentient consciousness, and imagination accompany reason and allow people to become “fully cognizant of a circumstance or situation playing out in real time and space” (p. 95). Modern education, though, focuses on “mental consciousness” (p. 96) at a cost to these other modes of knowing. Emotion and imagination can dominate a child through the junior-high years, and only as the child reaches the higher ages of 14 to 17 (8th to 11th grade) do the sentient and imaginative form a “dynamic tension” within the mind. To avoid an overemphasis on ego consciousness, Mitchell argues that “holistic education [can] teach young people not to sacrifice the earlier modes of consciousness to domination by the ego” (p. 96). Part of the way Mitchell encourages this is by interacting with his students in the community where they live. He also incorporates teaching strategies such as the use of storytelling, art, and drama. His goal is to get students to follow certain basic precepts: 1. Know yourself; 2. Be true to yourself; 3. Be comfortable with your way of learning; 4. Discover the courage to become increasingly independent from a materialistic and egocentric view of reality.

The goals of teaching, then, involve the following:

keep[ing] the balance between the sacred and social trusts while teaching the four purposes of education in the classroom—occupational skills that encourage an individual’s vocational calling, socializing the common beliefs, attitudes, values and behaviors by teaching them from a humanist perspective, teaching the universal humanist values of all cultural identities, and helping children achieve their highest holistic potential by recognizing the archetypal characteristics in their personalities. (p. 107)

Stimulation of the “highest holistic potential” is approached through awakening the “heroic archetype” that “resides in the soul of the adolescent” (p. 107). It is integral to the emergence of the adolescent ego as the teen attempts to move away from conscious and unconscious parental attachments. It incorporates the search for a “vocation that serves the continuity of culture” (p. 107), a goal that is too often distorted in contemporary culture through social and traditional media and through peer pressure. Mitchell here addresses teaching experiences around Santa Cruz, California, a countercultural refuge that offered “a natural rapport between adults and young people” (p. 110) similar to what he had found in Mexico. In his geometry classes Mitchell has students intermingle right-brain and left-brain skills through combining the measuring of physical forms with their relation to and use in the creative process. He also recalls utilizing fairy tales outside the classroom to help students whose home circumstances impinge on their classroom performance. Stimulating the archetype allows him to achieve an “interrelatedness [with students] that is described as *participation mystique*: a mysterious, soul-to-soul level of sentient and imaginative dialogue that transcends the ego, a *transindividual* relationship” (p. 115). These experiences, and perhaps the laid-back nature of the Santa Cruz community, allowed Mitchell to build relationships with students that “went beyond the role of the professional teacher and came closer to the concept of a sacred trust” (p. 118), wherein a nonparental adult participates in the “growth, development, and maturity of young people” (p. 118). Such relationships involve seeing metaphysical aspects of the soul that are too often masked by “adolescent ego facades” (p. 119). Mitchell evokes these relationships through case studies of individual students, claiming that the failure to nurture the archetype and the souls of children can lead to personality disorders that get expressed in behaviors from hyperactivity and lethargy to the extremes of drug use, suicide, and mass shootings. These manifestations are often attributed to the “wounding of the inner child,” but Mitchell cautions against such interpretations, as they imply “the failure of adults in the family, the schools, and the community to adequately nurture the souls of children” (p. 127). The struggles, as Mitchell describes them, referring to Erik Erikson, are to establish trust, resolve the struggle between self-doubt and self-certainty, control adolescent shame and guilt, and teach students how to finish tasks.

Various case-studies suggest approaches to completing these tasks, including some that involve complicated interactions with the adolescent. Mitchell even becomes a substitute parent when he has a troubled student live with him. This strategy backfires, though, and Mitchell eventually has to ask the teen to leave. He also presents an incident when he accompanies children in a late-night exploration of a cave. His chanting increases the “religious significance of the adventure” (p. 144). Such experiences emphasize Mitchell’s point that “learning begins with a participatory experience in which the teacher stimulates the students’ feelings and imaginations with appropriate archetypal metaphors that can later be examined using rational consciousness” (p. 145). A teaching methodology addressing composition adapted from one presented by Poincare involves the steps

of identification, inflation, subordination, negation, and creation—terms used to outline strategies that help students identify themes, brainstorm, subordinate ideas, engage in small-group workshops, and develop final works.

Mitchell concludes the book with two general recipes for working with adolescents: First, using creativity in teaching via the introduction of storytelling, art, and drama, and second, helping students explore the archetype of the hero, which essentially represents the developmental process all teenagers go through. The archetype’s “spiritual message is conveyed through the soul-to-soul *participation mystique* between adult storyteller and the child,” through which storyteller, auditor, and material fuse, forming “transindividual relationship at the level of soul consciousness” (p. 157). Cultivation of transindividual relationships requires that the teacher explore the archetype of the teacher—a non-parental adult figure who aides in “the child’s differentiation from the parents and bonding with the social collective” (pp. 161-162). “The objective of achieving independence from the parents and from the mass psyche requires the guidance and nurturance of nonparental adults” (p. 162). Such relationships can be fulfilled by adult relatives or other adults, but the teacher, “seeking the vocational archetype within him or herself ... nurtures the souls of children in the classroom in a nonparental, reciprocal, archetypal relation with one or more of the students in the class” (p. 262). Mitchell warns against authoritarianism or manipulation in the classroom, as these can “[undermine] the soul’s archetypal authority over the child’s developing personality” (p. 163). The good teacher nurtures the soul of the child, and “is defined by an archetypally grounded self-identity that is deeply ingrained into the psyche as the guide of his or her own holistic personality.... [T]he good teacher is, literally, ‘called’ to [the] vocation by the voice of his or her inner guiding spirit” (pp. 166-167). Mitchell concludes,

The real objective of education can be realized by transforming the education process to one that emphasizes holistic personality development within the framework of the sacred trust [that] embraces the archetypal relationships that nurture the souls of our children. (p. 169)

While the insights offered by the book are salutary, there may be some limitations to the approach Mitchell offers. One involves the potential scope of the archetypal aspirations Mitchell proposes. The current standard class size in intermediate- and upper-grade levels in Chicago Public Schools is 30 to 32 students,¹ while in Santa Cruz high schools the average ratio of students to teacher is 20 to 1.² Perhaps it is not for nothing that Rousseau, in *Emile*, describes the education of one child by one master. Transindividual relationships and participation mystique in their original, anthropological context certainly involve group phenomena. But often Mitchell separates out students at the individual level, as the emphasis on case studies shows. Generally a classroom presents a complicated social dynamic. The strategies used to stimulate archetypal interactions, such as storytelling, may be socially amenable and lead to group involvement. And notably all teachers who care tend to have distinctive relationships with individual students, so that the dynamic driving a relationship between an individual student and a teacher can be complicated

¹ Chicago Public Schools Policies and Rules, <https://www.cps.edu/sites/cps-policy-rules/policies/300/301/301-2/#:~:text=27%20%2D%2029%20in%20kindergarten%20classes,classes%20and%20upper%20grade%20classes,2024>. Accessed 4 November 2024.

² Santa Cruz City High School District, <https://www.niche.com/k12/d/santa-cruz-city-high-school-district-ca/>. Accessed 4 November 2024.

and, in our litigious society, sometimes hazardous. The socio-psychological processes compounded by the classroom dynamic—if the teacher cares, as Mitchell clearly does—can be profound. But in the book, such relations are often most clearly expressed at the individual level of interaction between one teacher and one student, or at least one at a time. Fuller exploration of the social dynamic involved in incorporating archetypal material into the classroom would be good. But this might go beyond the scope of this largely personal account of Mitchell's experiences as a teacher.

Also, the brief commentary on private schools, linking them to the utilitarian focus of the national mandates that centralize materials available for teaching, might be misleading, as this passage seems to assume a conservative slant to the privatization movement. This is in fact most likely currently the case. But it need not always be so, and the utilitarian focus need not drive conservative educational motivations. Religious fundamentalism, for instance, is not utilitarian in the sense Mitchell means, or is so only insofar as it drives the agenda of the supporting parties. Beyond these minor concerns, though, Mitchell's work is certainly worth consideration for its insights into the mind of the teacher, and provides genuine insights for the person who is thinking of pursuing a career in teaching.